

Perspectives of managerial competencies and challenges on managerial functions: A basis for productivity training program

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Abstract

The study determines the perspectives of managerial competencies and challenges on managerial functions as basis for productivity training program of the managers of the selected small and medium enterprises in the city of Bacoor relative to their competencies, challenges, and the recommendations that may be proposed to further improve competencies in performing their managerial functions. The study employed the descriptive method and utilized the survey questionnaire as the primary source of data. The statistical tools used were the frequency count, percentage, weighted and average mean. The findings revealed that the managers perceived themselves to be “competent” in terms of self-awareness, customer service, problem-solving, leadership, and communication wherein all the indicators listed on each area were “often” done or applied by them in their work. The major challenges encountered along their basic management functions include: preparation of operational plans, arrangement and display of products, provision of timely coaching and mentoring to the staff in need and monitoring individual performances. As a measure to overcome those challenges, training workshops on the mentioned challenges experienced may be initiated by the management of the selected small and medium enterprises.

Keywords: Managers; managerial competencies; challenges.

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Introduction

Businesses now face a variety of difficulties in the fast-paced, internationally focused markets of the world. Efficiently managing the many business processes without micromanaging, generating undue delays or disputes within these operations, is one of the major problems—and also one of the most difficult to overcome (Vitez, 2022). There are many schools of thought regarding how to approach the difficulty of integrating multiple business functions into a management plan.

The recently industrialized economy of the Philippines is considered to be one of the fastest growing in the world. Numerous sizable international firms seeking to cut expenses and benefit from competitive local salaries and a highly educated workforce have found a home in the business sector. The restaurant sector was reportedly generating over 600 billion pesos in income in 2019 alone, and it was expanding quickly (Nuestro, 2020).

It appears that management is the focus of the modern world. It implies that effective administration is responsible for all, or nearly all, of the world's advancements. It promotes initiative and creativity, efficient use of resources, and less waste. Employee morale is raised, relationships and teamwork are strengthened, productivity is increased, absenteeism and turnover are decreased, and workers' quality of life is enhanced (Akroni, 2011).

The Philippines is ranked 138th out of 185 economies by the World Bank and International Finance Corporation (IFC), despite the nation's numerous modernization efforts. This presents significant challenges for the ease of doing business and emphasizes the value of local knowledge. And the restaurant business was the most severely wounded by the Covid-19 pandemic, with a full recovery expected by 2025 (Lumabad, 2021).

In the new normal, adjustments were made such as developing productivity training programs. It is from this standpoint that the researcher was motivated to conduct a study, which reminds about the type of management that is needed right now in the modern world, especially during the pandemic. Understanding management's functions—which requires first examining what management is all about—is one method to approach this problem. When it comes to how management practices affect a company's success, high-achieving organizations' excellent management is frequently emphasized in academic and popular discussions about business (Saporta-Eksten, 2017). Considering that compared to certain other corporate divisions, management lacks the same precise responsibilities. However, management has specific roles to direct operations, much like every other aspect of business (Belyh, 2019).

Without a doubt, management techniques affect a company's performance and production, according to Battisti and Iona (2009). Research results are contradictory, nevertheless. Therefore, the lack of agreement among experts regarding the impact of implementing complementary management approaches may stem from problems with measurement or from the depth of study. Therefore, more investigation is required. Specifically, for a multi-level strategy that starts at the lowest aggregate level and ends at the firm level of analysis to evaluate how management practices affect a firm's productivity.

Therefore, due to the importance and relevance of the managers in the retail business, the researcher prompts to study the perspectives of managerial competencies and challenges on managerial functions of the selected supermarkets in Bacoor City as applied and experienced in their day to day activities in their respective departments or sections. Bacoor City is primarily chosen as the locale of the study because of the on-going developments in infrastructures, and amenities that serve as indicators that the city is rapidly growing and developing. Retail industry in Bacoor city plays a big part of its economic growth. The growth of retail industry in the city cannot be denied as evidenced by the rise of different business establishments, such as franchised stores, food service industries, malls, department stores, and supermarkets. Before, big department stores can be found only in the key cities. But now, these can be seen in different places in the country.

In Bacoor City alone, there are already small and medium enterprises that are competing for their market. Hence, this study was conducted to gather data from the managers of the selected small and medium enterprises in Bacoor City relative to their managerial competencies as well as the different challenges and problems that confront them. Furthermore, the researcher chooses to conduct the study in three small and medium enterprises in the City of Bacoor.

The researcher aims to find the performance of the managers with the use of the different leadership styles relative to the productivity in the new normal in order to gain insights necessary in supporting the company's operation through analytical understanding and help them enhance their managerial competencies. The use of effective and efficient managerial skills becomes a growing global phenomenon in every organization. Furthermore, this study will serve as an avenue for the business leaders to empower the members of the team in the midst of pandemic. With the different issues noted, this study is being conceptualized.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to determine the relationship of leadership styles and productivity in the new normal of the managers at the selected small and medium enterprises in Bacoor city. Specifically, this study seeks answers to the following problems:

1. What is the profile of the managers of the selected small and medium enterprises in the city of Bacoor in terms of:
 - a. age,
 - b. civil status,
 - c. educational attainment,
 - d. position in the company, and
 - e. number of years in service?
2. What are the perspectives of the managers of the selected small and medium enterprises in the city of Bacoor relative to their competencies in the following areas:
 - a. Self-awareness,
 - b. Customer service,
 - c. Problem solving,
 - d. Leadership, and
 - e. Communication?
3. What challenges do managers face in the selected small and medium enterprises in the city of Bacoor relative to their managerial functions in terms of:
 - a. Planning,
 - b. Organizing,
 - c. Staffing and directing, and
 - d. Controlling?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the managers' profile relative, and their managerial competencies?
5. What training needs may be proposed to further improve the productivity in performing their managerial functions?

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between the managers' profile relative to their managerial competencies along the different areas.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This study invited only thirty (30) managers to join the survey. Since the total number of managers cannot be determined due to non-disclosure policy of the management of the selected small and medium enterprises, the researcher invited only ten (10) willing managers from each of the three selected small and medium enterprises included in the study. Other managers in the retail industry in the city of Bacoor were not included in the study to delimit its scope.

Methodology

The researcher utilized the descriptive method of research to determine the relationship of leadership styles, and the productivity performance of managers in the new normal at the selected small and medium enterprises in the city of Bacoor. Descriptive method of research according to Macombies (2019) aims to describe a population, situation or phenomenon accurately and systematically, and it could answer what, when, where, when and how questions, but not why questions.

Descriptive-correlational design of research was used in this study. This method was used to describe the data from the derived frequencies, percentages, and other statistical calculations. The descriptive design was used in profiling and characterization of the respondents, while the correlational design was used to determine the significant relationship established by the salient findings.

Data Collection

The primary source of data in this study was gathered from the respondents' responses from the survey questionnaire. Nonetheless, the secondary sources of data were gathered from journals, theses, dissertations from local, foreign, and online resources that contributed to the conceptualization process of the present study.

Respondents of the Study

In order to determine the relationship of leadership styles and the productivity of the managers in the new normal, the respondents are the managers from SM Supermarket, Robinsons Supermarket, and Puregold Supermarket in the city of Bacoor.

Research Instrument

The researcher prepared a questionnaire, which was first validated, then pilot tested with .80 reliability. The questionnaire has four parts. The first part indicates the profile of the respondents. The second part refers to the perspectives of the managers in relationship to the leadership styles and productivity with a scale of 5 – Very High, 4 – High, 3 – Average, 2 – Low, and 1 – Very Low. The third part refers to the challenges faced by the managers, and the fourth part pertains to the training needs that could be proposed to further improve their productivity at work.

Data Analysis Procedure

The researcher individually requested approval to carry out the study from each supermarket's management. After receiving approval, the researcher went to the Human Resource Department to obtain the managers' list. The questionnaires were distributed to the respondents by the researcher, who asked them to complete all of the questions honestly. The surveys were individually obtained by the researcher. To ascertain the respondents' perceptions, the collected data were totaled, tabulated, and a weighted mean was calculated.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The statistical phrases and formula were used to assess the study's findings. The weighted mean was used to indicate the relative presence of the set of results in relation to the totality, while frequency and percentage were utilized to construct the respondents' profile. The weighted mean and frequency distribution were used in the investigation. A data presentation that indicates the percentage of observations for each data point or cluster of data points is called a percentage frequency distribution. It is an especially helpful way to represent other data, such as the distribution of survey responses. Conversely, the weighted mean can be thought of as a form of average. Certain data points give the final mean more "weight" than others, rather than every data point contributing equally. Each of the values in the data set are then multiplied by the corresponding weights, added up, and divided by the total number of replies to obtain the calculated mean or average.

Furthermore, the investigator employed the chi-square test to see if a noteworthy correlation exists between the respondents' profiles and their managing responsibilities. A particular instance of the gamma distribution is the chi-square distribution, often known as the chi-squared distribution. A gamma distribution with $a = n / 2$ and $b = 0.5$ is equivalent to a chi square distribution with n degrees of freedom.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Profile of the managers (N=30)

Indicators	Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age	21-25	10	33.33
	26-30	14	46.66
	31-35	4	7.50
	36-40	1	3.33
	Above 40	1	3.33
Civil Status	Single	16	53.33
	Married	14	46.66
Educational Attainment	Graduate Studies	7	23.33
	College Graduate	23	76.66
Position in the Company	Manager	18	60.00
	Assistant Manager	12	40.00
Number of Years in Service	2 – 5 years	12	40.00
	6 – 10 years	14	46.66
	11 years and above	4	13.33

Table 2 presents the profile of the managers. According to the table, in terms of age, most of the managers are from 26-30 years old (46.66%), while others are from 21-25 years old (33.33%), and 31-35 years old (7.50%). Each of the respondents were aged about 36-40 years old and above 40 years old, respectively. In terms of civil status, majority of them were single (53.33%), while others were married (46.66%). In terms of educational attainment, most were college graduates (76.66%), while some had their graduate studies (23.33%). In terms of position in the company, majority were managers (60.00%), while some of them were assistant managers (40.00%).

Leadership Styles of Managers on Different Perspectives Relative to Management Functions

Table 3 presents the perspectives of the respondents on their competency along self-awareness. Self-awareness is defined as knowing one's internal states, preference, resources, and intuitions. It went beyond merely accumulating knowledge about oneself. In this study, self-awareness was characterized as the key cornerstone to emotional intelligence. The results showed that the managers always understand

their strengths and weaknesses, with 4.89 weighted mean. However, they sometimes recognize their personal issues, with 3.36 weighted mean. This means that the managers of the selected small and medium enterprises in city of Bacoor are aware and understand their actions in the performance of managerial function, however, they needed to be more adept in dealing with their personal issues and problems.

Table 2. Perceived competency on self-awareness (N=30)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Understands my own strengths and weaknesses	4.89	Always
Recognizes that I have personal issues at times	3.36	Sometimes
Does not allow work to be affected by personal problems	3.86	Often
Transparent in all my actions	3.82	Often
Fast learner and willing to learn new things each day	4.32	Often
Easily adapts to changes in the working environment	4.13	Often
Makes use of personal experience as learning avenue for improvement	3.53	Often
Recognizes individual differences among the staff	3.66	Often
General Weighted Mean	3.94	Sometimes

Legend: 1.00-1.49 – Never; 1.50-2.49 – Seldom; 2.50-3.49 – Sometimes; 3.50-4.49 – Often; 4.50-5.00 – Always

According to this study, the fundamental building block of emotional intelligence is self-awareness. Furthermore, in order to maintain excellent psychological health and a positive attitude on life, self-aware people generally behave actively rather than respond passively (Goleman & Boyatzis, 2017). Tekleab et al. (2008) go on to say that followers' supervisory satisfaction and leader effectiveness are correlated with self-awareness of transformational leadership. On the other hand, followers' self-leadership is connected to their self-awareness of empowering leadership. Self-awareness has an impact that goes beyond how leadership directly affects the outcome variables.

Table 3. Perceived competency on customer service (N=30)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Interacts well with both internal and external stakeholders	3.39	Sometimes
Listens to customer's suggestions, comments, and complaints	4.16	Often
Accords equal treatment to customers	5.00	Always
Provides timely information to customers about matters that concern them	3.96	Often
Always put me in the shoes of the customers	3.86	Often
General Weighted Mean	4.13	Often

Legend: 1.00-1.49 – Never; 1.50-2.49 – Seldom; 2.50-3.49 – Sometimes; 3.50-4.49 – Often; 4.50-5.00 – Always

Table 3 shows the respondents perspectives on the competency along customer service. The figures reveal that they “always” accord equal treatment to customers. This means that they provide fair treatment to all customers regardless of their looks, race, gender, etc. The results also reveal that they “often” listen to customer's suggestions, comments, and complaints, with 4.16 weighted mean; “often” provide timely information to customers about matters that concern them, with 3.96 weighted mean; and “always” put themselves in the shoes of the customers, with 3.86 weighted mean. However, they need to improve their competence in interacting well with both internal and external stakeholders, since the results showed that they “sometime” practiced along this indicator, with an adjectival value of 3.39.

According to Miller (2010), providing for the demands of consumers is what customer service is practically defined as. However, from a psychological viewpoint, it also includes showing customers respect and caring for them. As a result, every business wants to provide customer service that goes above and beyond what the client expects. Cuong and Khoi (2019) strengthened the idea that customer happiness is positively impacted by service quality.

Table 4. Perceived competency on problem solving (N=30)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Recognizes and faces problems as it occur	3.89	Often
Exerts effort to solve problems / conflicts at own level	4.16	Often
Looks into the root of any problem and/or conflict that arise in the department / section	4.09	Often
Employs thorough analysis of the pros and cons of actions and/or decisions	3.59	Often
Takes full responsibility of own actions and decisions	4.00	Often
General Weighted Mean	3.94	Often

Legend: 1.00-1.49 – Never; 1.50-2.49 – Seldom; 2.50-3.49 – Sometimes; 3.50-4.49 – Often; 4.50-5.00 – Always

Table 4 shows that the perspectives of the managers on their competency in problem-solving. As shown in the table, the managers “often” recognize and face problems as it occurs (3.89); “often” exert efforts and solve problems at their levels (4.16); “often” look or study the root of a problem or conflict (4.09); employ thorough analysis of the pros and cons of actions and decisions (3.59); and take full responsibility of actions and decisions (4.00).

This shows that managers learned how to manage problems and solved them at their levels. They may be trained well in this area before they were given the positions they handled. Their professional experiences may also have influenced their problem-solving abilities, as problem-solving is a skill that is applicable to all industries and positions. Not every employee were proficient at addressing problems, even if everyone had to do so at work (Rios et al., 2020). According to Szarucki (2013), managers at all levels have to explore a variety of options in resolving organizational issues. As a result, choosing the right approach to address a given managerial issue is crucial.

Table 5. Perceived competency on problem solving (N=30)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Compels the staff to follow orders and instructions without exerting much authority	4.76	Always
Sees to it that the voice of the staff are heard	4.46	Often
Gets the desired result with the help of my staff	4.33	Often
Consults the staff about measures to better improve their jobs	4.26	Often
Employs coaching and mentoring among staff who are in need	4.16	Often
Rewards deserving staff for a job well done	3.56	Often
Imposes disciplinary measures among the staff when needed	3.86	Often
Sees to it that every member of my staff is involved in the work of our team to achieve our goals	3.82	Often
Encourages my staff to continue to learn new things for their own personal development	3.46	Sometimes
General Weighted Mean	4.07	Often

Legend: 1.00-1.49 – Never; 1.50-2.49 – Seldom; 2.50-3.49 – Sometimes; 3.50-4.49 – Often; 4.50-5.00 – Always

Table 5 presents the perspectives of the managers on leadership competency. The results show that they perceive themselves as good leaders as they compel their staff to follow their orders and instructions without exerting much authority, with a weighted mean of 4.76, interpreted as “Always”. As holders of supervisory positions, it is expected that they have good leadership qualities, as they could not have gotten positive participation from their team. Without leadership, all of the other company assets were ineffectual. Leadership is recognized as the key component that allowed everything to function together flawlessly (The CEO Institute, n.d.).

They also “often” perceive themselves as managers who see to it that the voice of their staff are heard (4.46); “often” get desired results with the help of their staff (4.33); “often” consult their staff about measures to better improve their jobs (4.26); “often” employ coaching and mentoring among their who are in need (4.16); “often” reward deserving staff for a job well done (3.56); “often” impose disciplinary measures among their staff when needed (3.86); “often” see to it that their staff are involved in the work of the team to achieve our goals (3.82); and “sometimes” encourage their staff to continue learning new things for their own personal development (3.46). According to Mistarihi (2021), effective leadership is necessary in the modern era of increasingly chaotic situations, freshly developing issues, and disasters like the Covid-19 pandemic.

According to Talukder and Hawkins (2014), New Zealand managers place a higher value on communication and interpersonal skills than on coaching and technical abilities, and they consider "on the job experience" to be the main source of upskilling. The qualities that managers value the most include reliability, honesty, and integrity; inventiveness is viewed as the least desirable quality. Directors and owners must push management to view creativity as an essential quality that boosts innovation and competitiveness. Furthermore, Navarro and Bundoc (2013) argue that a company's leadership capability is one of its most important elements. Every level of an organization must be committed to the complicated process that is the dynamics of managerial competencies.

Table 6. Perceived competency on communication (N=30)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Informs the staff of the goals that are needed to achieve as a group	4.36	Often
Maintains open line communication with the staff and peers	4.40	Often
Openly express concerns about the department to the upper management	4.09	Often
Informs the staff of their shortcomings, weaknesses, and possible measures to improve	4.36	Often
Relays information from upper management to my staff promptly	4.16	Often
General Weighted Mean	4.27	Often

Legend: 1.00-1.49 – Never; 1.50-2.49 – Seldom; 2.50-3.49 – Sometimes; 3.50-4.49 – Often; 4.50-5.00 – Always

Table 6 shows the perceived competency of the managers in communication. Both indicators “informs the staff of the goals that are needed to achieve as a group”; and “informs their staff of their shortcomings, weaknesses, with possible measures to improve” receive the highest weighted mean of 4.36. It shows that managers are open and true to their staff. In this way, effective communication serves as important for the development of an organization. The results reveal that the managers “often” perceive all the indicators with the general weighted mean of 4.27.

Since business involves constant interactions with various parties, including managers, employees, and clients, communication is, in fact, the foundation of any organization's success. Moreover, efficient communication guarantees the exchange of information among all pertinent stakeholders, mitigating the likelihood of misinterpretation, discontent, and distrust (Vaughan, 2017). According to Bjekic et al. (2013), one of the most important qualities for managers to have in order to carry out their professional duties in any business effectively is communication competency.

The discussion on whether there is a significant relationship between the profile of the managers of the small and medium enterprises, and their managerial functions are presented below. Figure 1 shows that ρ -value is equal to 0.733, which is greater than the value of $\alpha = 0.05$. It can be inferred that the age of the managers of enterprises is not related to the degree of their competencies in the area of self-awareness.

Chi-Square Test for Association: Age_1, Self-Awareness

Rows: Age_1	Columns: Self-Awareness			
	Always_1	Often_1	Sometimes_1	All
21-25	30 27.67	20 26.00	30 26.33	80
26-30	37 38.04	40 35.75	33 36.21	110
31-35	10 11.76	13 11.05	11 11.19	34
Above 36	6 5.53	5 5.20	5 5.27	16
All	83	78	79	240

Cell Contents
Count
Expected count

Chi-Square Test

	Chi-Square	DF	P-Value
Pearson	3.581	6	0.733
Likelihood Ratio	3.659	6	0.723

Figure 1. Chi-Square Test for Association: Self Awareness

Figure 2 shows that p -value is equal to 0.989, which is greater than the value of $\alpha = 0.05$. It can be inferred that the age of the managers of enterprises is not related to the degree of their competencies in the area of customer service.

Chi-Square Test for Association: Age_CS_1, Customer Service

Rows: Age_CS_1	Columns: Customer Service			
	Always_CS_1	Often_CS_1	Sometimes_CS_1	All
21-25	15 16.560	16 15.947	15 13.493	46
26-30	24 22.680	22 21.840	17 18.480	63
31-35	9 7.920	7 7.627	6 6.453	22
Above 36	6 6.840	7 6.587	6 5.573	19
All	54	52	44	150

Cell Contents
Count
Expected count

Chi-Square Test

	Chi-Square	DF	P-Value
Pearson	0.904	6	0.989
Likelihood Ratio	0.904	6	0.989

Figure 2. Chi-Square Test for Association: Customer Service

Figure 3 shows that p -value is equal to 0.993, which is greater than the value of $\alpha = 0.05$. It can be inferred that the age of the managers of enterprises is not related to the degree of their competencies in the area of problem-solving.

Chi-Square Test for Association: Age_PS_1, Problem-Solving

Rows: Age_PS_1 Columns: Problem-Solving

	Always_PS_1	Often_PS_1	Sometimes_PS_1	All
21-25	14 14.133	13 14.133	13 11.733	40
26-30	24 24.733	27 24.733	19 20.533	70
31-35	8 7.420	7 7.420	6 6.160	21
Above 36	7 6.713	6 6.713	6 5.573	19
All	53	53	44	150

Cell Contents
Count
Expected count

Chi-Square Test

	Chi-Square	DF	P-Value
Pearson	0.767	6	0.993
Likelihood Ratio	0.763	6	0.993

Figure 3. Chi-Square Test for Association: Problem Solving

Figure 4 shows that the p -value is equal to 0.158, which is greater than the value of $\alpha = 0.05$. It can be inferred that the age of the managers of enterprises is not related to the degree of their competencies in the area of leadership.

Chi-Square Test for Association: Age_L_1, Leadership

Rows: Age_L_1 Columns: Leadership

	Always_L_1	Often_L_1	Sometimes_L_1	All
21-25	29 30.99	32 32.63	28 25.38	89
26-30	48 41.43	38 43.63	33 33.94	119
31-35	7 13.23	21 13.93	10 10.84	38
Above 36	10 8.36	8 8.80	6 6.84	24
All	94	99	77	270

Cell Contents
Count
Expected count

Chi-Square Test

	Chi-Square	DF	P-Value
Pearson	9.287	6	0.158
Likelihood Ratio	9.380	6	0.153

Figure 4. Chi-Square Test for Association: Leadership

Figure 5 shows that p -value is equal to 0.692, which is greater than the value of $\alpha = 0.05$. It can be inferred that the age of the managers of enterprises is not related to the degree of their competencies in the area of communication.

Chi-Square Test for Association: Age_C_1, Communication

Rows: Age_C_1 Columns: Communication

	Always_C_1	Often_C_1	Sometimes_C_1	All
21-25	13 17.280	18 16.640	17 14.080	48
26-30	29 24.120	21 23.227	17 19.653	67
31-35	6 6.840	8 6.587	5 5.573	19
Above 36	6 5.760	5 5.547	5 4.693	16
All	54	52	44	150

Cell Contents
Count
Expected count

Chi-Square Test

	Chi-Square	DF	P-Value
Pearson	3.885	6	0.692
Likelihood Ratio	3.897	6	0.691

1 cell(s) with expected counts less than 5.

Figure 5. Chi-Square Test for Association: Communication

Based from the results, it can be concluded that the age of the managers of small and medium enterprises is not related to their perspectives relative to managerial competencies. Using the chi square test, the expected frequency of any item should be not less than five (Nazim, n.d.). Hence, in using chi square, there is insufficient data to test the relationship of civil status, educational attainment, position in the company, and length of service to the respondents’ perspectives.

Challenges that Managers Experience Relative to Management Functions

In the performance of managerial functions, challenges always if not often happen. This part presents the challenges, and problems experienced by the managers in the discharge of their basic management functions.

Table 7. Challenges that managers experience relative to planning (N=30)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Preparation of operational plans	3.46	Sometimes experienced
Difficulty in establishing strategies to achieve objectives	3.02	Sometimes experienced
Evaluating and comparing previous plans against accomplishments	3.26	Sometimes experienced
Lack of support from top management	2.12	Seldom experienced
Limited resources	2.35	Sometimes experienced
General Weighted Mean	2.84	Sometimes experienced

Legend: 1.00-1.49 – Not experienced; 1.50-2.49 – Seldom experienced; 2.50-3.49 – Sometimes experienced; 3.50-4.49 – Often experienced; 4.50-5.00 – Always experienced

Table 7 presents challenges and problems the managers face in terms of planning. Planning in this study refers to the process of setting the objectives of the team and identifying strategies on how to achieve them. The findings reveal that the managers “sometimes experience” preparing the operation plans (3.46); establishing strategies to achieve objectives (3.02); evaluating and comparing previous plans against accomplishments (3.26); and shows limited resources (2.35) at their disposal.

However, they “seldom experience” support from the top management. Since planning is seen as crucial to an organization's success, it has been recognized as fundamental in the field of management. Because it is the foundational function of management, planning is regarded by many as the most important managerial function. By evaluating an organization's goals and methods for reaching them, planning helps them become ready for both the future and the present (Bigelow & Pratt, 2022).

As a result, managers dedicate a large portion of their time to making plans for any eventuality that may arise within the company. Usually, a manager might draft a plan with the intention of achieving certain company objectives, like raising sales or enhancing customer satisfaction. It is crucial to remember that planning is a continuous process that can become very specialized depending on the objectives of the team, department, division, and organization. It may be the manager's responsibility to determine whether objectives within their particular domain require planning. Moreover, a manager's main task is to find innovative solutions to issues. The four main functions of management principles—planning, organizing, leading, and controlling—draw from a range of academic fields and assist managers in rising to the occasion of innovative problem solving.

Table 8. Challenges that managers experience relative to organizing (N=30)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Demand for long work hours	3.12	Sometimes experienced
Assignment / rotation of staff duties	3.32	Sometimes experienced
Arrangement / displays of products	3.69	Often experienced
Systematic work process of the staff	3.48	Sometimes experienced
Too much work during peak hours	3.45	Sometimes experienced
General Weighted Mean	3.41	Sometimes experienced

Legend: 1.00-1.49 – Not experienced; 1.50-2.49 – Seldom experienced; 2.50-3.49 – Sometimes experienced; 3.50-4.49 – Often experienced; 4.50-5.00 – Always experienced

Table 8 shows that the managers “sometimes experience” demand for long working hours (3.12); assignment / rotation of staff duties (3.32); systematic work process of the staff (3.48); and too much work during peak hours (3.45). Also, the respondents “often experience” arrangement / displays of products, with 3.69 weighted average mean. Belyh (2019) asserts that management is a component of the company that is not as specifically responsible as certain other divisions. Nonetheless, management has specific roles to direct operations, just like every other department in the company. Therefore, management is viewed as a social process that needs people leadership along with the effective use of resources in order to accomplish a certain organizational goal. It involves accountability for achieving the goals and serving certain organizational purposes through sensible, efficient planning and governance.

Essentially, management is a dynamic process that involves many different components and activities. The dynamic and social nature of management implies that its functions are distinct from those of operations. Operational functions include things like marketing, finance, and purchasing, whereas management functions are different based on the level of the organization at which they were performed.

Table 9 shows that managers “sometimes experience” limited knowledge of staff in the job (3.13); fast employee’s turn over (3.16); lack of training among the staff and newly hires, (3.26); timely coaching and mentoring the staff in need (3.43); evaluation of individual staff performance, and timely feedback (3.29); and punctuality of staff (3.02). However, the respondents “seldom experience” poor reward system for performing employees, with 1.91 weighted mean.

Table 9. Challenges that managers experience relative to staffing and directing (N=30)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Limited knowledge of staff in the job	3.13	Sometimes experienced
Fast employee's turn over	3.16	Sometimes experienced
Lack of training among staff and newly hires	3.26	Sometimes experienced
Timely coaching and mentoring to staff in need	3.43	Sometimes experienced
Poor reward system for performing employees	1.91	Seldom experienced
Evaluating individual staff performance and providing timely feedback	3.29	Sometimes experienced
Punctuality of staff	3.02	Sometimes experienced
General Weighted Mean	3.14	Sometimes experienced

Legend: 1.00-1.49 – Not experienced; 1.50-2.49 – Seldom experienced; 2.50-3.49 – Sometimes experienced; 3.50-4.49 – Often experienced; 4.50-5.00 – Always experienced

Because of factors including the complexity of human behavior, the growth of businesses, technological advancements, and others, staffing has become more important in recent years. Placing the appropriate individual in the proper job is the primary goal of staffing. Furthermore, Koontz et al. (2019) concurred that the administrative function of staffing requires manning the organizational structure by means of appropriate and efficient personnel selection, evaluation, and development to occupy the responsibilities outlined in the structure. Additionally, it is the aspect of the managerial role that drives organizational strategies to be effective in achieving organizational goals. It is regarded as the enterprise's lifeblood, igniting human activity because staffing, organizing, and planning are merely steps toward completing the task at hand. The inert-personnel component of management known as direction focuses on directly influencing, directing, overseeing, and inspiring subordinates to meet organizational objectives. Supervision, encouragement, leadership, and communication are all parts of direction.

Table 10. Challenges that managers experience relative to controlling (N=30)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Wide span of control	3.02	Sometimes experienced
Cross-checking on staff	3.32	Sometimes experienced
Monitoring individual's performance	3.89	Often experienced
Monitoring team's performance	3.35	Sometimes experienced
Implementing and controlling strategies and measures	3.49	Sometimes experienced
General Weighted Mean	3.14	Sometimes experienced

Legend: 1.00-1.49 – Not experienced; 1.50-2.49 – Seldom experienced; 2.50-3.49 – Sometimes experienced; 3.50-4.49 – Often experienced; 4.50-5.00 – Always experienced

Table 10 shows that managers “sometimes experience” wide span of control, (3.02); cross-checking on staff (3.32); and implementing and controlling strategies and measures (3.49). However, the respondents “often experience” monitoring individual's performance, with 3.89 weighted mean. Merchant (2006) states that management's main responsibility is to guarantee that plans are followed out or, if circumstances dictate, that they are adjusted after strategies are established and plans are created, which is the essential managerial control role. As management entails supervising others' actions, ensuring that others are carrying out their duties is a significant component of the control function. Whenever and whenever it exists, the fundamental control process consists of three parts, such as setting standards, gauging performance against these standards, and resolving deviations from plans and standards. When a management control system identifies and highlights substantial deviations from the original plan for the individuals responsible for making the necessary corrections, it effectively incentivizes action. Therefore, it is possible that this emphasis on feedback and measurement is really inaccurate.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study aims to determine the relationship of leadership styles and productivity of the managers in the new normal at the selected small and medium enterprises in Bacoor City. A great majority of the managers of the selected small and medium enterprises in the City of Bacoor are college graduates with age ranging from 21 to 36. It may be construed that managers at the selected small and medium enterprises in the city of Bacoor are qualified for the managerial positions, who apply the different leadership styles in its daily operation. However, they need to attend training for them to acquire more knowledge and skills especially the latest trends in the retail industry. A training on managerial functions is proposed by the researcher in enhancing their leadership skills relative to productivity in its operations.

Training workshops may be provided by the management to address the challenges encountered or experienced by the managers of the selected small and medium enterprises in the city of Bacoor, e.g., operational plan preparation, performance appraisal, and evaluation. While it is true that the beneficiary of the training is the individual himself, in this case, the managers will grow personally and learn new things, but the organization will likewise benefit from the services of the trained and highly competent managers, which will redound to better performance and ultimately higher sales and higher profits.

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